

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

D2.4. SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

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Authors	Prody Mwemena, Enrique Nieto
Work Package Leader	AEIDL
Project Coordinator	ECORYS

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1. Introduction

This document presents the links to all the SHERPA social media accounts, to fulfil the requirements of the Deliverable 2.4 – Launch of Social Media Accounts by the end of Month 2 of the project. Further information about the strategic use of each of the Social Media accounts presented below is described in the D2.1: Strategy for project Stakeholder Engagement, Communication and Dissemination.

2. Social Media Channels

2.1. Twitter

 [@rural_interfaces](#). A dedicated SHERPA Twitter account has been created **to communicate instantly and engage with our target audiences** from society, science and policy stakeholders. This channel will be used for short news flashes, using a clear and crisp style, not too descriptive or institutional.

Twitter has become increasingly popular with academics as well as students, policymakers, politicians and the general public. Many users struggled to understand what Twitter is and how they could use it, but it has now become the social media platform of choice for many.

Furthermore, dedicated hashtags will allow streamline communication of specific products and actions e.g. #SHERPAComms #SHERPAEvent, #SHERPAPolicyPaper, #SHERPABlog, etc. The use of hashtags will help people connecting outside of physical meetings and exchange about them.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the SHERPA twitter account

2.2. LinkedIn

LinkedIn will facilitate **networking** for people and professional organisations from the target audience mainly belonging to the private sector and academia. We have created an account to help our connections stay up to date with SHERPA developments and to share information with relevant stakeholders. As pointed out on the LinkedIn website, LinkedIn is the world's largest professional network in more than 200 countries and territories worldwide.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/rural-interfaces>

We will ensure that LinkedIn page is properly used by:

- Sharing status update to ask questions to people in the network or share news or insight (in relation with the Twitter timeline).
- Identifying more people, companies, researchers, policy-makers, etc., potentially interested by the project's results and engaging with them,
- inform about events and meetings organised under this Strategy.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the SHERPA LinkedIn account

2.3. Facebook

A dedicated SHERPA Facebook account was created with the aim to reach out to SHERPA stakeholders, and those not fully covered by LinkedIn.

<https://www.facebook.com/RuralInterfaces/>

This channel will be adopted for public outreach and showcasing outputs. Events, Photo album, and livestreaming functionalities will be exploited, as appropriate.

Facebook Pages can be a valuable marketing tool. Public pages can be used to attract and retain interested audiences through the use of regular updates. They can also act as a multiplier as posts are shared and their interactive dimensions are exploited to facilitate conversation. Facebook pages also offer the possibility of paid promotion to generate new targeted audiences.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the SHERPA Facebook page.

2.4. Instagram

This channel will be used **to share visual outputs** (i.e. on the ground snapshots shared by project partners), and also for ad-hoc actions such as the Annual EU events.

<https://www.instagram.com/ruralinterfaces/>

Figure 4: Screenshot of the SHERPA Instagram account

2.5. Youtube

A dedicated SHERPA YouTube channel has been created **to publish and collect all the project's multimedia products**. Videos will be embedded via YouTube on the website, and easily shared on social media through short links.

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC3r8V-tCwFVHiOVDIXGHuxg?view_as=subscriber

Figure 5: Screenshot of the SHERPA Youtube account

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